

ANALYSIS OF THE EDGE EFFECT ON FLOW PATTERNS IN LIQUID COMPOSITES MOLDING

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ABSTRACT

In liquid composites molding, often, the cutting of the fiber preform is not precise enough and leaves a small clearance between the reinforcement and the mold edges. This clearance creates a preferential flow path for the resin which may disrupt the filling of the mold cavity. Experience has shown that even a small clearance of 1 or 2 mm could have a significant effect, especially if the preform has a high fiber content. Hence a model is needed to predict this channeling effect in order to take it into account in computer simulations of the mold filling process.

In this paper a model is presented to describe this phenomenon. The idea is to characterize simultaneously the flow in the channel and through the reinforcement. The model is derived using Navier-Stokes equations in the open channel and Darcy's law in the porous preform. From this model, an equivalent porous medium is defined for which an equivalent permeability tensor can be computed as a function of the channel geometry. Numerical simulations performed with the computer software RTMFLOT developed in our laboratory for liquid composite molding have shown that in some limit cases, i.e., a large channel (5 - 6 mm) or for very low porosity reinforcements, the transverse flow from the channel to the preform can be neglected in the model and still predicts quite well the flow edge effect. In other cases however, namely for a clearance of intermediate size (2 - 3 mm) which is a common case in RTM, or for a higher porosity of the reinforcement, the transverse flow from the channel to the rest of the preform must be taken into account. Experimental data to validate the proposed model are also presented.

INTRODUCTION

Let us consider a clearance " d " between the edge of the reinforcement and the mold edge as shown in figure 1. The edge effect is defined by comparing the flow velocity u_c in the channel between the porous medium and the mold edge and the flow velocity u_m inside the porous reinforcement.

Figure 1. Schematics of the edge effect on the fluid velocity.

The velocity u_f in the channel is defined as a function of the physical parameters governing the flow: d (channel width), k (permeability tensor of the porous medium), μ (viscosity of the fluid), G_m and G_f defining the absolute value of the pressure gradient in the flow direction for the porous medium and the open channel respectively. Navier-Stokes equation which governs the flow of the fluid in the open channel is used in conjunction with the Beavers-Joseph equation which establishes an interfacial connection between the open channel equation and Darcy's law for the porous medium. For a non compressible and viscous fluid having a low velocity, the inertia terms are neglected and the Navier-Stokes equation for an open channel becomes :

$$\rho \frac{Du_f}{Dt} = \rho g + G_f + \mu \nabla^2 u_f \quad (1)$$

where D/Dt refers to the material derivative, ρ is the density of the fluid and g the gravity vector. If we consider a steady flow in a horizontal channel, then the left end side of equation (1) and the gravity term vanishes. The equation is then reduced to the following linear and scalar expression :

$$\frac{\partial^2 u_f}{\partial y^2} = - \frac{G_f}{\mu} \quad (2)$$

which gives after integration :

$$u_f = - \frac{1}{2} \frac{G_f}{\mu} y^2 + Ay + B \quad (3)$$

where A and B are constants.

At the interface between the channel and the reinforcement, Beavers and Joseph [1] assume a proportional relationship between the derivative of u_f with respect to y and the slippage occurring at the interface between the fluid velocity in the open channel and the Darcy's velocity in the porous preform. Using that assumption, the following relation can be written :

$$\left[\frac{\partial u_f}{\partial y} \right]_0^+ = \frac{\alpha}{k^{1/2}} [u_f(0^+) - u_m] \quad (4)$$

where $u_f(0^+)$ is the velocity of the fluid at the interface, k is the permeability of the porous medium in the flow direction, u_m is the Darcy's velocity also in the flow direction and α a dimensionless quantity defined by Beavers and Joseph as being dependent of the material parameters which

characterize the structure of the permeable material within the boundary region. The value of α which must be obtained experimentally is close to unity for most reinforcing materials [1,2,3]. The Beaver-Joseph formula was validated by K. Vafai and R. Thiygaraja [4], who presented an analytical solution of the velocity profile in the open channel, in the porous medium and the transition zone. However, according to Vafai and Tien [5], the empirical term α must be determined by an analysis of the pressure gradient if the non linear inertia term is to be considered in Navier-Stokes equation to model the open channel flow. In our case and according to Beavers and Sparrow [6], this is not necessary, since the Reynolds number is assumed to be less than unity.

The transition distance "e" at the interface between u_f and u_m shown in figure 1 is very small and in most cases it can be neglected when compared to the clearance "d" [1,2,3]. In addition, the derivative of the velocity in the x direction with respect to y should be continuous at the interface. Based on this and using a Taylor expansion about the parameter u_f in equation (2) and replacing in equation (4) gives :

$$e = \frac{k^{1/2}}{\alpha} \tag{5}$$

Since α is close to one, we can conclude that "e" is in the order of the square root of the permeability k. From equations (3) and (4) and since we consider no slippage at the edge, i.e., $u_f(d) = 0$, the value of u_f can be obtained as follows :

$$u_f = - \frac{G_f}{2 \mu} \cdot y^2 + \frac{\frac{G_f}{2\mu} \cdot d^2 - u_m}{d + e} \cdot y + \frac{\frac{G_f}{2\mu} \cdot e \cdot d^2 + u_m \cdot d}{d + e} \tag{6}$$

Since we want to integrate the edge effect in a computer simulation model, it is preferable to express the velocity for the fluid flow in the channel in a Darcy's law form which is the following :

$$u = - \frac{k}{\mu} \nabla p \tag{7}$$

In doing this, the clearance channel could be considered as a virtual porous medium of permeability k_c , where k_c is the equivalent permeability tensor of the edge effect. Since $u_f(d) = 0$, equation (6) can be rewritten as follows :

$$u_f = - \frac{\nabla p}{\mu} \left(-\frac{1}{2} \cdot y^2 + \frac{d^2}{2 (d + e)} \cdot y + \frac{e \cdot d^2}{2 (d + e)} \right) + \frac{u_m}{d+e} \cdot (d - y) \tag{8}$$

We know that a typical permeability value for a fabric is in the order of 10^{-9} m^2 , and since the value of "e" is comparable to $k^{1/2}$, then $e \approx 10^{-4.5} \text{ m}$ and can be neglected in equation (8) when compared to $d \approx 10^{-3} \text{ m}$.

In the channel, most of the flow occurs in the region surrounding the maximum value of u_f which is located in the neighborhood of the center of the channel. In that zone, we can say that u_f is sufficiently larger than u_m to neglect the contribution of u_m in equation (8). If we express u_f in a Darcy's law form, we have :

$$u_f = - \frac{k_c}{\mu} \cdot \nabla p \tag{9}$$

Following the approximations previously discussed and comparing equation (9) with equation (8), we obtain the following expression for k_c :

$$k_c = \frac{1}{2}(y \cdot d - y^2) \quad (10)$$

Now, the velocity in both domain is expressed in a Darcy's law form. If we replace equation (10) in equation (9) and integrate across the channel, we obtain the total flow. Then dividing by the channel width d , we can calculate an average flow from which the equivalent average permeability of the channel is defined :

$$k_{c, ave} = \frac{d^2}{12} \quad (11)$$

Lee and Fong [7] present a more complex expression for the equivalent permeability. However, for channel sizes between 1 and 3 mm which represents practical cases, there is no significant difference between their expression and equation (11) which is much simpler. Then, as a concluding remark, we can say that when the transverse flow is neglected, the equivalent permeability of the channel is a unique function of its geometry.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Flow experiments were conducted with a non stitched fabric (JB Martin 82675). This is a balanced fabric having two plies at 90° . These plies are stitched with three polyester yarns, two of these yarns being stitched together in the warp direction, the other one intersects them on one side of the fabric in the weft direction. The fabric has a surface density of 320 g/m^2 distributed as follows: 48.5 % in the warp and 44.3 % in the weft. The remainder 7.2 % is constituted by the polyester yarns. The fluid used in the experiment is corn syrup with an average viscosity value of 90 cp. The corn syrup offers the advantage of being a Newtonian fluid, which can be cleaned easily from the mold cavity. Two hardened rectangular glass plates with an aluminum picture frame form a cavity of 120 mm in width by 930 mm in length. A pressure transducer is mounted near the inlet port and a hydraulic cylinder mounted on a traction-compression machine is used as a pumping unit. To ensure a straight flow front at the beginning of the reinforcement impregnation, the reinforcement is positioned about 6 cm away from the injection port.

The permeability of the fabric in both principal directions should be measured using the unidirectional flow method [8]. When this is done, the material is ready for the experimentation with an edge effect. For the JB Martin 82675, the measured value for the permeability in both direction is 0.710^{-9} m^2 . In order to create a clearance between the reinforcement and the mold edges, samples of 5 plies of JB Martin 82675 were cut at varying width, from 114 to 119 mm, leaving a clearance value on one side ranging from 1 to 6 mm. For the experiment, five plies of fabric were used and the liquid was flowing in the warp direction of the reinforcement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Flow simulation of the edge effect was done using the RTMFLOT simulation software developed in our laboratory [9]. In order to verify the applicability of the equivalent permeability model given by equation (11) for the edge effect, five experiments with channels size ranging from 1 to 6 mm were conducted. It was found that when comparing the calculated and measured filling time and flow front shape, the theoretical $k_c = d^2/12$ gave good agreement with the experimental results for the larger channel of 5 and 6 mm. For the smaller ones, the theoretical value needs correction and

the equivalent permeability has to be determined otherwise. In order to do so, the equivalent permeability for the channel were obtained by trial and error using the RTMFLOT software. This was done assuming that when an injection is performed at a constant flow rate, the ratio between the equivalent permeability k_c in the channel and the permeability in the preform k in the flow direction tells how the fluid is shared between the two. Knowing this, it is possible to calculate the time taken by the fluid to reach a given point in the channel. Then, this calculated filling time can be compared with the experimental value. When the ratio $r = k_c/k$ to fit the experimental filling time is found, k_c can be calculated since the permeability k of the reinforcement is already known. To illustrate this, Figure 2 shows the simulation and the experiment for a clearance of 3 mm.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. Simulation and experiment for a clearance of 3 mm.

These results show that the RTMFLOT software has the capacity to reproduce very well the flow front shape and especially the point where the flow front reaches the opposite side of the cavity. This point is an other reference for the exactness and the quality of the simulation.

Table 1 shows the values for k_c using the simulation method for channel sizes of 1, 2 and 3 mm. For channel size of 5 and 6 mm when the theoretical k_c value of $d^2/12$ is used in the simulation, it gives a good agreement with the experiment. At this point in our research, we have yet no way to know in advance for a given fabric and a given channel size when the theoretical value of $d^2/12$ can be used for k_c . In practice, the width of the channel may vary slightly. The third column of table 1 shows the range of values for $k_c = d^2/12$ assuming a ± 0.3 mm variation in the precision of the preform cut. Of course, this variation has a much larger influence on the smaller channels.

Table 1: Equivalent permeability values for various channel size when using the JBMartin 82675.

Channel width d (mm)	k_c from simulation ($10^{-8}m^2$)	$k_c = d^2/12$ ($10^{-8}m^2$)	$k_c = d^2/12$ for $d \pm 0.3$ mm ($10^{-8}m^2$)
1	2.0	8.3	4- 14
2	5.1	33.3	24 - 44
3	7.1	75	60 - 90
5	-	208	184 - 234
6	-	300	270 - 330

ANALYSIS OF THE TRANSVERSE FLOW

The equivalent permeability $d^2/12$ defined by equation (11) for the edge effect ignores any transverse loss of fluid from the channel to the preform. It is clear that such losses decreases the velocity of the fluid in the open channel. As seen in figure 2, and schematically shown in figure 3, a transition distance is created between the flow front in the open channel and the straight flow front in the preform. As seen during the experiment, this transition distance is much larger than the quantity "e" defined by equation (5) for no transverse flow and shown in figure 1.

Figure 3. Schematic of the transverse flow in the y direction.

When performing injection experiments, three basic kind of flow profiles are observed. In the first one, shown in figure 4, the fluid flow from the channel to the preform is negligible and the small transition zone is well described by the distance "e" defined earlier by equation (5) for no transverse flow.

Figure 4. Flow profile for the first case with almost no transverse flow.

This limit case could be representative of a preform of extremely low transverse permeability or for a large channel beside a preform with a regular permeability. In fact, it was observed with the fabric tested at a fiber volume fraction of 0.26, that when the channel size is relatively important, i.e., 5 or 6 mm, the propagation inside the channel is so fast that the transverse flow does not have the time to develop as seen in the simulation of figure 5 and $k_c = d^2/12$ gives good results.

Figure 5. Flow simulation with a 6 mm channel.

For the second case shown in figure 6, the flow velocity in the channel is similar to the flow velocity in the preform and the distortion in the flow front shape is small. This is typical of a very narrow channel ($\approx 1\text{mm}$) beside a regular preform porosity. In that case, the $d^2/12$ for k_c gives acceptable results. This can also be seen when comparing the simulation and theoretical value for k_c in table 1 for that channel size.

Figure 6. Flow profile for the second case where flow velocity is similar in both region.

Figure 7. Flow profile for the third case with significant transverse flow.

For the third case shown in figure 7, the perturbation caused by the transverse flow cannot be neglected. In our tests, this occurred for clearance sizes of 2 and 3 mm. As seen in table 1, for these clearances, the theoretical value given by $d^2/12$ was almost 10 times larger than k_c obtained with the procedure described earlier using RTMFLOT. In such a flow profile, one can expect that the transverse flow will be affected by the transverse permeability k_y . In order to investigate this, additional flow experiments were performed on another fabric, the JB Martin 81011. This fabric has a transverse permeability of $0.03 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{m}^2$ which is much smaller than the JB Martin 82675 which has a permeability of $0.7 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{m}^2$. Two channels size of 2.5 and 3 mm were considered.

Table 2 : Equivalent permeability for small channels beside the 81011 and 82675 fabrics.

Fabric type	k_v (10^{-9}m^2)	d (mm)	$k_c = d^2/12$ (10^{-7}m^2)	k_c from simulation (10^{-7}m^2)
82675	0.7	2	2.4 - 4.4	0.51
82675	0.7	3	6.1 - 9.1	0.71
81011	0.03	2.5	4 - 6.5	5
81011	0.03	3	6.1 - 9.1	7

As shown in table 2, for the 81011, the k_c value obtained by trial and error from the simulation method is very close to the theoretical value of $d^2/12$ for no transverse flow. When comparing the results for both fabrics with the same channel size, it is obvious that no general conclusion can be drawn for the applicability of the $d^2/12$ value for k_c . This applicability is clearly a function of the channel size as well as the transverse permeability of the fabric.

CONCLUSION

In this paper a theoretical model assuming no transverse flow was presented to evaluate and predict the edge effect phenomenon in liquid composite molding. The results shown that in several cases, this model predicts quite well the edge effect. In some other cases however, the perturbation caused by the transverse flow from the channel to the preform cannot be neglected. In these cases, a back calculation using the flow simulation software RTMFLOT along with experiments is proposed. When analyzing experimental flow profiles, it was observed that they can be divided in three cases. For two of them, transverse flow is negligible. In the first one, typical of a larger channel, the flow in the channel is so fast that the transverse flow does not have the time to develop. In the other case, typical of a very small channel, the flow velocity is almost the same in the channel and the reinforcement. In the third case, transverse flow cannot be neglected and a significant transition zone is developed. Finally, it was shown that the applicability of the no transverse flow model is a function of the channel size and the reinforcement permeability. However, more work is needed to predict the applicability of $k_c = d^2/12$ for the equivalent permeability of a channel beside a reinforcement having a given permeability.

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